

THE ROLE OF THE MARKETING PROGRAM IN INCREASING THE EXPORT COMPETENCE OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

E-mail: musaeva_shoira@mail.ru

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Abstract. In this article, in the "market strategy of the enterprise" section, the possibilities of selling in the selected market, the expected profitability of the activity in the selected target market, and the volume of the planned sales of the enterprise are considered.

Keywords: Enterprise, product, competition, market, sales, profitability, program, strategy.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается «рыночная стратегия предприятия» рассматриваются возможности сбыта на выбранном рынке, ожидаемая рентабельность деятельности на выбранном целевом рынке, объем планируемых продаж предприятия.

Ключевые слова. Предприятие, продукт, конкуренция, рынок, продажи, рентабельность, программа, стратегия.

INTRODUCTION The strategy of innovative development of the market of light industrial products enables the economic assessment of the export potential of the industry based on the formation of demand and supply and opportunities of the market of sewing products, the study of the domestic and foreign markets, and the formation of an information and advertising system. In our opinion, forecasting the supply and demand for network products, increasing the volume of processing of natural fibers, preparing new types of fabrics based on innovations, forming new production technologies based on adaptation to local raw materials should be among the main directions of the development strategy of the sewing products market. In the implementation of this strategy, the training of highly qualified personnel, their continuous training and retraining are of particular importance. Because no matter how good the ideas are,

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. In the context of reforms carried out in our country, development of proposals for improving the marketing program for increasing the export of knitted products:

researching theoretical aspects of competitiveness in the international market;

critical study of international competition terms and their improvement;

To study the tasks, competitiveness trends and current issues of the textile industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

determine the characteristics of marketing activities and marketing program in the international market;

In the analytical function of marketing research, the factors of the external environment, the market, its elements and situation, consumers, the market, the product and the structure of the product, as well as the internal environment of the firm are analyzed. Factors controlled by the company's management are taken into account - technological process, financial situation, organizational structure, market selection, etc. External environmental factors include

uncontrollable factors such as consumers, competition, government, economy, technology, independent media.

The reduction of centralized planning bodies in the textile industry in a market economy requires independent movement in the formation and maintenance of branched and complex relationships. Accordingly, it is necessary to use the methods of market segmentation to produce effective plans for the development of the textile industry.

Market segmentation is the process of segmentation of consumers and sellers of textile products according to their demands and reactions in the market. The concept of marketing in the field of sales arises from the fact that sellers use a product in different ways and buy it based on different motivations. It is necessary to move to the maximal adjustment of the production and trade activities of the textile industry to the requirements of specific consumers. The main goal of consumer market segmentation is to group all consumers into one type of product as much as possible.

The segment of the consumer market must meet a number of requirements:

1. Each segment should be clearly described.
2. It is necessary to determine the specific requirements of consumers for each segment.
3. It is necessary to determine the specific characteristics of consumers.
4. The defined segment of consumers must be large enough to cover the costs of the product manufactured to satisfy consumer demand.
5. The segment must be suitable for the company to sell the product it produces

In our opinion, the main directions of the strategy of innovative development of the market of light industrial products should be:

1. Formation and development of light industrial machinery; re-equipment and modernization of existing enterprises; establishment of new high-tech enterprises.
2. Formation of demand and supply and opportunities of the market of light industrial products, study of domestic and foreign market, formation of information and advertising system, economic assessment of export potential, forecasting of supply and demand for industry products.
3. Increasing processing of natural fibers, preparation of new types of fibers based on innovations, formation of new production technologies based on adaptation to local raw materials.
4. Creation of new jobs based on the training of highly qualified personnel, continuous training and retraining, expansion and re-formation of branch enterprises.

The importance of marketing research in the organization, management, planning and control of overall marketing activities is one of the main features of modern marketing theory. High-level organization of marketing research is the first stage, that is, the "base point" in determining and implementing the marketing strategy of enterprises and organizations, the set of methods used in their scope, analytical and processing processes. In today's environment, where the consumer market is increasingly enriched with new goods and services, the importance of marketing research in identifying new opportunities and using them wisely is increasing day by day.

Consumers-buyers can buy all types of goods and resources produced in the community. Therefore, the total size of the social product, including the preparation of the means of production, is the main determining factor of marketing.

In the innovative development of the light industry of our republic, marketing research can be carried out in five major directions:

- firstly, by carrying out research on the organization of advertising, that is, to inspire buyers, test advertising, types of advertising and increase their comparative effectiveness;

- secondly, through strategic planning and organizational policy, i.e. making short and long-term forecasts, analysis of enterprise results and market opportunities, new diversification development opportunities, analysis of operational gross and internal environment of the organization, as well as conducting export market observations;

- thirdly, by conducting research on the responsibility of the organization, that is, increasing the social responsibility of the organization in terms of customer formation and environmental protection;

- fourthly, to analyze the market, that is, to carry out work on the attitude of buyers to new goods, potential and opportunities of new goods, testing of new goods, problems of packaging of goods and its inspection;

- fifthly, researching sales opportunities, conducting marketing research, that is, identifying potential or potential markets, analyzing market composition, sales volume changes, conducting test marketing, conducting sales promotion studies.

Of course, each organization carries out marketing research in one direction or another according to its capabilities and goals. It takes into account the organization's strategy for a certain period, required tactical actions. A company's goal is usually expressed in the form of financial indicators, and these indicators give an idea of what the company wants to achieve over a certain period of time, for example, one year, two years, and five years.

In our opinion, there are other economic incentives to attract investments in the light industrial sector. These are, first of all: the presence of huge resources of raw materials, mainly high-quality cotton fiber; low cost of the energy network; availability of qualified and relatively inexpensive labor resources; developed network of communication; banking and legal branches of services; such as the presence of large and untapped markets selling ready-made textile products in the region (the population of Central Asian countries is more than 55 million people) and wool and semi-finished products in the European Union countries.

In determining the company's goals, it is necessary to take into account various factors, in particular, the intentions of the shareholders, the competition, the strengths and weaknesses of the company, resources, etc. "Can the company achieve its goals by using available resources and operating in existing markets?" To find an answer to the question, it is necessary to conduct a special analysis. Based on such an analysis, the goals and tasks of each department are determined. Taking into account production possibilities, it is necessary to analyze the financial situation, the established policy in relation to employees, and the distribution channels of goods. When analyzing a separate sector, plans should be developed for each department, with estimated values of inputs and outputs, and focused on specific goals,

Figure 1. Scheme of marketing activities of textile enterprises.

The planning process in marketing, along with the analysis of external factors, also requires the study of the enterprise, that is, the internal analysis. By studying the enterprise, it should answer the questions of whether the level of training of sales managers meets the requirements, the condition of the equipment, and whether the quality of our goods is satisfactory compared to that of competitors.

The importance of the marketing program in the proper organization of marketing activities and its implementation is incomparable. This program consists of several sections, and

in the "market strategy of the company" section, the company's main competitive advantages are determined and the possibilities of sales in the selected market are evaluated. For this, the following specifications are defined:

- the expected profitability of the activity in the selected target market;
- the size of the company's planned sales;
- dynamics of the firm's market share;
- demand dynamics and potential demand size.

The company's competitive advantages can be characterized by product, price level, range of services, effectiveness of sales channel, communication policy in accordance with current conditions and popularity of its brand among potential buyers. In this section of the program, it is also necessary to assess the availability of resources (financial, production, marketing, human) for the activity of this company in the selected market. The following authorities are taken into account when developing the commodity policy:

- product novelty level;
- product range;
- the number of similar goods or substitute goods in this market segment;
- the degree of its correspondence to the needs of specific buyers of this market segment;
- product quality;
- technological complexity;
- the level of requirements for pre-sale and after-sale service;
- the feasibility of standardization or commodity flexibility;
- patent protection and patent purity for a new product;
- compatibility of the existing organizational structure of the company with the new production;
- the size of the costs of creating a new product;
- mandatory product certification in the target market;
- profitability of production and sale of new goods in the target market;
- investment payback period;
- the period of assimilation of the new assortment and its optimization;
- costs per product etc.

When developing a sales policy, the following are taken into account:

- application to the sales network for this market segment;
- the organizational structure of the company's sales and the number of qualified sales personnel;
- assessment of the enterprise's work experience in this market segment;
- assessment of the expediency of using the services of intermediaries;
- opportunities to increase the volume of sales with the help of intermediaries;
- the policy of intermediaries towards the firm;
- availability of financial resources to create a sales system;
- comparative assessment of profitability of personal selling system and alternative offers;

- supply of available goods to the market;
- number of potential customers;
- the nature of the distribution of the order;
- the habits and preferences of end consumers;
- volatility and instability of the commodity;
- coping efforts of the company's management;
- sales channel control, etc.

When developing a price policy, it is necessary to take into account the following:

- taking into account the practice of competitors, choosing a method of price organization that is consistent with the company's capabilities and goals;
- price level for one product;
- price dynamics corresponding to the stage of the product's life cycle;
- the price ratio in the product range (nomenclature) according to the novelty level, quality differences and technical level of the goods;
- price level relationship with competing similar goods in the target market;
- level of elasticity of demand;
- level of functional and pure competition;
- choosing a pricing strategy for launching a new product to the target market;
- service policy, brand popularity, length of sales channel and type of sales intermediaries, delivery conditions, discount system, etc.

3. In the "Communication policy" section, it is recommended to allocate the budget with the individual organizers of the policy of moving the goods to the market and to justify their choice, to solve the issues of communication means.

When implementing a marketing program and determining the budget, it is necessary to consider the following:

- the amount of total costs for the implementation of all marketing measures considered in this program;
- marketing research costs;
- costs of future market forecasting;
- costs for studying the company's own production and sales opportunities;
- costs for creating a marketing program;
- expenses for the salary of employees of the company's marketing department;
- the costs of paying fees for the services of special marketing and advertising organizations;
- costs of paying fees for the services of commercial intermediaries;
- costs to evaluate the initial and final effectiveness of this marketing program;
- costs and monitoring for the implementation of control in the implementation of the marketing program;
- costs for introducing current changes during the implementation of the marketing program, etc.

It should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan is constantly working on increasing the export potential of our Republic by creating incentives for exporters of goods.

In the near future, an important factor for strengthening the export potential of our Republic is the strengthening of economic stimulation, export support by the state.

Today, a number of tax incentives aimed at state support of exporting enterprises are provided. A regressive scale of taxation has been introduced depending on the share of exports in relation to the volume of sales of goods.

The share of export in the total volume of product sales: if it is from 15% to 30%, the rate is 30%; Above 30%, the rate is halved.

Property tax for exporting enterprises is also carried out depending on the share of exports in the total volume of products: from 15% to 25% - the rate is reduced to 30%. From 25% to 50% - the rate is reduced by 50%; If it is more than 50% - property tax is not charged.

When exporting a product, value added tax is charged at the lowest rate. Payment of value added tax on material and technical resources necessary for the production of exported products can be paid in arrears for up to 90 days without interest.

Implementation of credit financial support for national exporters is carried out in the following directions:

- creation of effective conditions of promotion of commercial banks financing export operations accepted in international practice;

- improvement of the existing mechanism of social protection of national exporters and commercial banks financing exports;

- providing investment insurance;

- one of the main obstacles in the export of products is that the produced products do not meet the international conditions for certification and standardization.

The second of the conditions for the effectiveness of the national export policy is to fulfill the following conditions that allow to increase the export potential of our country:

- training and retraining of national personnel;

- development and implementation of optimal and effective conditions of marketing research that allow to identify and develop new product markets;

- active acceleration of exports through the development of foreign trade infrastructure;

- introduction of advanced methods of export policy tactics and strategies of developed countries;

- development of a modeling system to determine the short-term and long-term perspectives of the state and dynamics of the parameters of the commodity markets in the main areas of the export activity of our republic;

- to develop a strategy for the development of new transport corridors in order to improve the efficiency of internal transport infrastructure and diversify export-import loads;

- to reduce the cost of transportation of export-import goods by developing the infrastructure and creating a system of pricing, and by handling the goods in the territory of the republic and in the main international seaports;

- improving the development of the contractual and legal basis of cooperation with foreign countries on trade, investments, development of new transport corridors, cargo transit;

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